

Puértolas-Pascual, E., Kuzmin, I. T., Serrano-Martínez, A., & Mateus, O. (2023). Neuroanatomy of the crocodylomorph *Portugalosuchus azenhae* from the late cretaceous of Portugal.

This study presents the first detailed description of the neurocranial anatomy and neuroanatomical analysis of *Portugalosuchus azenhae*, a eusuchian crocodylomorph from the Late Cretaceous of Portugal. Although it was originally classified as a possible Crocodylia and one of the oldest representatives of this clade, its phylogenetic position remains controversial. Using high-resolution microtomography images, this study aimed to improve the original description of the taxon and update the scarce neuroanatomical knowledge of Eusuchia and Crocodylia from this time interval, crucial to understanding the origin and evolution of these clades. The resulting three-dimensional models of the CT data allowed a detailed description of the neurocranium and well-preserved internal cavities. This made possible the reconstruction of the cavities of the olfactory region, nasopharyngeal ducts, brain, nerves, carotid arteries, blood vessels, paratympanic sinus system and inner ear, which made it possible to estimate some neurosensory capacities. Compared with other crocodiles, these analyzes demonstrated that *Portugalosuchus*, already in the Cretaceous, possessed olfactory acuity, vision, hearing and cognitive abilities within the range observed in other extinct eusuchians and modern crocodiles. Furthermore, the new anatomical data provided by the TAC were included in a phylogenetic analysis. The position of *Portugalosuchus* differs slightly from the original publication, now placing it in a Gavialoidea, within the Crocodylia clade.

Figure. Original fossil ML1818 and 3D models of the reconstruction of the bones and internal cavities of *Portugalosuchus azenhae*.

